

Role of Dietary Bioactives and Functional Foods in Combating Lifestyle Disorders and Micronutrient Deficiencies

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.20117527

Abstract:

Sedentary lifestyles, urbanization and poor eating habits are all closely linked to the sharp increase in lifestyle-related conditions like obesity, type 2 diabetes, cancer and cardiovascular illnesses. Functional foods have a huge impact on promoting good health and averting diseases along with their primary potential of providing the essential nutrients which are required by our body to maintain its regular functioning. Their dual benefits of supplying nutrition and improving overall well-being through the presence of bioactive substances such as polyphenols, carotenoids, omega-3 fatty acids, probiotics, prebiotics, alkaloids and terpenoids have garnered significant interest. Through the mechanisms such as antioxidant activity, regulation of physiological functions, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects, gut microbiome management and modulation of cellular processes dietary bioactives play a very significant role in disease prevention and health promotion. Their inclusion in the diet is of a lot importance due to their role in supporting long-term health outcomes and reducing the risk of chronic diseases.

Keywords: *Functional Food, Lifestyle Disorders, Dietary bioactives, Health.*

Introduction:

Ayurveda, the ancient science of life, has always placed more emphasis on maintaining health and preventing illness by adhering to a healthy diet and lifestyle than on treating and curing illnesses. “Swasthyashya Swasthya Rakshanam”, which means to preserve the health of the healthy, is the fundamental tenet of the Ayurvedic medical system, as opposed to Aturashya Vikara Prashamanancha, which means to treat the illnesses of the sick. The Ayurvedic classics describe the Dinacharya (daily regimen) and Ritucharya (seasonal regimen) for this reason (Chandola 2012). It is well known that Roga (sickness) is caused by disharmony in the Doshas—Vatu, Pitta and Kapha. And preserving harmony is the goal of Ayurvedic science.

Changes in our nutrition and way of life lead to changes in our Tridosha state, which will inevitably impact us and cause disharmony and lifestyle diseases. Nowadays, a lot of people suffer from lifestyle problems, which are essentially caused by not adhering to seasonal routines because of a lack of focus on seasonal traits (Thakkar et al., 2011).

Lifestyle disorders are long-term illnesses that are mostly caused by bad choices in how you live. These are things like smoking, binge drinking, bad eating habits, not exercising and being stressed. Lifestyle disorders are a major global health problem because they last a long time and get worse over time, unlike infectious diseases. Functional foods have emerged as viable alternatives for the prevention and treatment of a

variety of diseases. According to scientific estimates, stress and unhealthy lifestyles have a combined effect on the immune system, increasing the risk of infections, diseases including cancer, numerous cardiovascular ailments and cerebrovascular conditions. As people become more conscious of how diet affects health, there is a growing demand for functional foods and the use of nutraceuticals has grown dramatically. Certain bioactive components have been used as additions in functional foods, nutraceuticals and medications due to their antimicrobial properties as well as humoral and cell-mediated immunological functions, where their biological activities can aid in disease control and prevention. As a result, doctors, food manufacturers, academics and consumers are increasingly concerned about the medicinal potential of certain food constituents (Soumya et al., 2021).

When government organizations in Japan started endorsing foods with proven health advantages in the 1980s, the idea of functional food was born (Arshad et al. 2025, Arshad et al. 2021). A food can be considered functional if it has been sufficiently shown to positively impact one or more target functions in the body, going beyond adequate nutritional effects in a way that is connected to either the reduction of the risk of a disease or the state of well-being and health (Shambhavi & Mishra, 2024). Functional foods contain essential bioactive substances like polyphenols, carotenoids, omega-3 fatty acids, alkaloids, isothiocyanates, sterols, flavonoids, soy protein, fatty acids, prebiotics, probiotics, phytoestrogens and various minerals and vitamins, functional foods offer health benefits beyond basic nutrition (Arshad et al. 2025, Shaikh 2022; Topolska et al. 2021). Dietary bioactives are the food ingredients that are naturally occurring, obtained from both plant and animal sources, present in foods that have effect on one

or more metabolic pathways, thereby contributing to improved health and overall well-being.

Classification, Sources and Action of Dietary Bioactives:

One of the most common among the members of bioactive compounds found in plants are polyphenols which have significant antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties that are beneficial to human health. Numerous food sources, such as fruits like berries, apples, and grapes; vegetables like spinach, onions, and kale; and whole grains, include these secondary metabolites (Arshad et al. 2025; Pandey and Rizvi 2009).

Plants contain a broad class of polyphenolic compounds called flavonoids, which have strong physiological effects like antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and immunomodulatory properties (Ahmed et al. 2022; Liskova et al., 2020). According to Cory et al. (2018), these are significant functional foods in our daily diet since they have the capacity to produce a number of biological responses that may be beneficial to human health (Ahmed et al. 2022). By altering the amounts of blood lipids and interfering with their metabolism, phenolic substances appear to help prevent cardiovascular illnesses. The elevated blood cholesterol levels are a significant risk factor for atherosclerosis. Phenolics may inhibit the development of atherosclerotic plaques in arteries by lowering total cholesterol and triglycerides, raising HDL and lowering LDL (Koutelidakis et al., 2016).

Carotenoids mostly found in carrots, sweet potatoes, pumpkin, mangoes, papaya etc have vital roles in human nutrition and health in addition to their basic functions in plants. The dietary precursors of vitamin A, which is vital for the vision and immune system, are provitamin A carotenoids like β -carotene and α -carotene. Approximately one-third of preschoolers

worldwide suffer from vitamin A deficiency, which can have fatal consequences, including blindness. As antioxidants, dietary carotenoids lower the risk of a number of chronic illnesses, including cancer and heart disease (Sun et al., 2022, Eggersdorfer and Wyss 2018).

A class of important polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), omega-3 fatty acids are well known for their significant effects on metabolic, cognitive and cardiovascular health. The main sources of these bioactive lipids include plant-based foods like flaxseeds, chia seeds and walnuts, as well as fatty fishes like salmon, mackerel and sardines (Arshad et al., 2025). Terpenoids and alkaloids are two important classes of bioactive compounds found in plants, each with a variety of pharmacological properties. Alkaloids are nitrogen-containing secondary metabolites with antimicrobial, analgesic, neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory properties; they are prevalent in many medicinal plants like mint and basil (Arshad et al. 2025, Heinrich et al. 2021).

Human health is significantly influenced by the gut microbiome and probiotics and prebiotics are crucial modulators of microbial diversity and function. They improve microbiota composition, enhances the nutrient absorption playing a potent role in mental health via gut-brain axis (Arshad et al. 2025). Use of curd, buttermilk, kanji, garlic etc is of a lot importance.

Role of Dietary Bioactives in Preventing Lifestyle Diseases:

Poor diet, unhealthy eating habits, sedentary lifestyle, chronic stress and irregular sleep patterns are some of the conditions that lead to lifestyle disorders like Type 2 Diabetes, Hypertension, Obesity and Cardiovascular Diseases. In their management, the function of bioactive substances in regulating metabolic health has gained emphasis. These naturally

occurring compounds, which come in zoochemical, microchemical, and phytochemical forms, provide a variety of ways to affect important metabolic pathways, including those related to fat metabolism, insulin sensitivity and inflammation. The significance of bioactive chemicals in the prevention and treatment of certain chronic diseases is highlighted by research into their possible therapeutic benefits (Lam et al. 2025).

By disrupting insulin signaling and causing β -cell dysfunction, oxidative stress—which is mainly caused by an excess of reactive oxygen species (ROS)—plays a crucial part in the pathophysiology of obesity and type 2 diabetes (Lam et al. 2025, Ramadan et al. 2024, Li. Et al. 2024). By activating Nrf2 (nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2), a transcription factor that promotes the expression of endogenous antioxidant enzymes like superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase and glutathione peroxidase, phytochemicals like polyphenols (like curcumin) and carotenoids (like lutein) demonstrate strong antioxidant qualities. By neutralizing ROS, these antioxidants improve insulin signaling, lessen oxidative damage to cellular structures, and shield pancreatic β -cells from oxidative stress (Lam et al. 2025, Ming et al. 2020, Sahin et al. 2023, Zhang et al. 2023). Therefore, by enhancing insulin sensitivity and reducing β -cell dysfunction, phytochemicals contribute to the maintenance of glucose homeostasis (Lam et al. 2025).

Flavonoids, polyphenols and omega-3 fatty acids are examples of phenolic antioxidants found in functional foods which chelate pro-oxidant ionic metals and scavenge reactive oxidative species (ROS), thereby lowering inflammation and oxidative stress (Arshad et al. 2025, Abeyrathne et al. 2022; Uro-Chukwu et al. 2025). Berries, citrus fruits and condiments are examples of functional foods and dietary products

that can help prevent and treat heart-related conditions including hypertension (Adefegha et al. 2018). Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) found in fatty fish (salmon, mackerel, sardines), krill oil, algae-based supplements lowers triglyceride levels, reduces risk of hypertension & atherosclerosis (Arshad et al. 2025, Nassar et al. 2023). Alpha linolenic acid (ALA) present in flaxseeds, chia seeds, walnuts, soybeans provide cardiovascular protection and anti-inflammatory effects (Arshad et al. 2025, Rajaram 2014).

Food Technology Perspective:

The stability, effectiveness and distribution of bioactive chemicals in functional foods are all significantly influenced by food technology. The preservation, bioavailability and general usefulness of these chemicals are greatly influenced by processing techniques, formulation strategies and sophisticated delivery systems.

Food processing procedures such as heating, drying, fermentation, extrusion and storage can dramatically impact the stability and activity of bioactive chemicals. Many bioactives encounter limitations such as poor solubility, instability during digestion, fast metabolism and inadequate absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. Encapsulation is an advanced technology used to protect bioactive chemicals from degradation and improve their stability and bioavailability. It aids in targeted delivery, controlled release, hiding offensive flavors and extending shelf life. In order to improve the efficacy of delicate bioactive compounds, functional foods and nutraceuticals frequently employ techniques including microencapsulation, nanoencapsulation, spray drying and coacervation. Functional foods and nutraceuticals provide creative techniques to deliver health-promoting bioactives through the diet. Nutraceuticals are concentrated forms of these chemicals that are frequently sold as capsules, powders or fortified goods, whereas

functional foods are regular foods enhanced with bioactive components. Numerous items, including probiotic, prebiotic, fortified cereals and foods enhanced with omega-3 fatty acids, have been made possible by advancements in food technology. These food products bridge the gap between nutrition and medicine by giving specific health benefits like higher immunity, better gut health and a lower risk of chronic diseases.

Conclusion:

Diets and functional foods have emerged as promising solutions for the prevention and treatment of numerous illnesses throughout the past ten years. Bioactive peptides are being studied as a functional meal that promotes health. Food proteins have been demonstrated to provide health advantages in addition to fulfilling the body's nutritional requirements (Soumya et al. 2021). Bioactive substances derived from plant extracts and natural foods have amazing therapeutic and supplemental qualities. These biologically active ingredients, which include carotenoids, probiotics, prebiotics and omega-3 fatty acids, provide a variety of health advantages, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, enzyme inhibition and gut microbiota modification properties. The creation, characterisation and targeted administration of these therapeutically and nutritionally relevant natural substances have been transformed by contemporary food science and technology (Arshad et al. 2025).

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